

IS ENES3 Data Request Review, Oct 8th

Joined: Martin, Alison, Karl, Klaus, Charlotte.

Apologies:

JOIN: <https://ukri.zoom.us/j/94141797908>

Context

- Previous meetings:
 - September:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/11ZHAUpzNv3TTVnEh4VklxpzaHf4ef6cryXlkxgnnsCc/edit#heading=h.n5pjmsuclfwe>
 - July:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wylSpCAzd3C5jFccpd0HGIEoQJsKAdnLW69hF5fg0EU/edit?usp=sharing> ;
 - [20th May, 2020](#) (also <https://zenodo.org/record/3901310>).
- IS-ENES3 M10.2 [Data Request Schema 2.0](#)
- Reference documents ([google sheet](#)).

Agenda

1. Discussion of variable prioritisation with CMIP Panel/WGCM
2. IS-ENES3 Milestone document on data request schema;
3. Registry of (horizontal) grids.
 - Useful first step might be to tackle vertical grids: list of available CMOR options is given here:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Njhnp-rAhQNb9lo4d_0YFUOdPttcPpjQec4R_7BMUH8/edit#gid=1854910047;

Karl: in the past CMIP has been open to all grids; it up to us to decide on requirements for grids. For CMIP6 we wanted tools, but that didn't happen.

If requirements are complex, we have a big problem. If we keep the requirements simple, the implementation is simple.

E.g. data on lat-lon grid;

Martin keeping it simple is difficult ...

Klaus: ocean grids in CMIP6, looked at areacello. Starting from list of ocean experiments and models: some groups publish fx for all variants but most only publish for one member and not always r1i1p1f1 → groups prefer to publish fx for only one member.

Looking at latitude and longitude, ignoring bounds. Hash of points to get UID ... as maybe expected, usually distinct models have distinct grids .. sometimes use same latitudes. Measure of difference: grid hash like a perceptual hash (similar → similar hash) [converts each value to a byte and rescale to 8x8 to get a 64 byte hash].

Karl: do all the IPSL grids get identified as identical when they should be?

Klaus: yes .. Char hash verified this.

Should we nudge modellers to use standard grids?

Karl: we did talk about this for regridded that, but didn't reach conclusion.

Modeling centres don't like the idea of multiple variants for fx fields.

Should think about changing this aspect of request.

Could as for fx/Ofx fields earlier, before main data submission -- tied to model, rather than simulation.

CVs have descriptive information.

ES-DOC has got capacity for good information; simplified since CMIP5 (because of feedback).

Martin: AtmosChem grid maybe much smaller than atmos grid ... should data be stored on this grid?

Karl: it is more convenient to use atmos grid ... but maybe should get grid on lower resolution.

Klaus: esmvaltool can do regridding ..

This is more of a framework, rather than a file level tool like CDO;

Klaus: Karl offered a short note on regridding guidance ... 90% there.

Klaus: there is no time varying version of the areacella/o fields .. as there is for others;

Martin: true .. a bug in the data request.

Dealing with duplicate areas: should this be allowed? Can we advise that it should be avoided? Can lead to incorrect diagnostics if not detected before analysis.

Recommendations:

- (1) Avoid requesting repeated fx fields -- request one per model;
- (2) Avoid duplication of output points in grids.
- (3) Try to complete the regridding guidance.
- (4) Complete "Harmonization of file naming .." with section on fx fields.

- (5) Develop a guidance document on grids . (cf existing recommendations https://docs.google.com/document/d/1kZw3KXvhRAJdBrXHhXo4f6PDI_NzrFre1UfW_GHISPz4/edit_)

Appendix different approaches to comparing grid

A: Using a hash

Results from Klaus.

Hash of latitude followed by hash of longitude followed by list of models;

```
1 4feb0c2c139d2195caa4129da428c25032f45442442de22c8834a34a58e4c084
0f333afbe2c993a69e7a4a8153120244bd9ecd063e5c6b31fa632e237f9e2675
    11 NCAR/cesm2
    1 NCAR/cesm2-fv2
    2 NCAR/cesm2-waccm
    2 NCAR/cesm2-waccm-fv2
1 4feb0c2c139d2195caa4129da428c25032f45442442de22c8834a34a58e4c084
dd648be6b28a6f55c1b6f9952ac47d52c10a049c40165db7999bb2126215357d
    1 NASA-giss/giss-e2-1-g
1 73dd9d569995575a7c4f15f4b8cc17821370b0c3ee51636b8898a0fc5b4f5130
b6d58e42f50c0e54b40e0bcb29a5e3f5b2ad582a4eb2f37dd848e2106bafdb26
    2 NOAA-gfdl/gfdl-esm4
1 89b31913691061ca4b5f22e93c7dd99c62e78ac759507731be45995746424b5d
e8a18acd3ee0f39f87ce31d560425d8609f37713b889e4bd1c43843d297538d4
    2 UA/MCM-UA-1-0
2 06e6371207c731663034a460df8156a4910044190604139fc6a7e254ad4c49cf
af7c355fa11abd4d49c743eb35c6d006a08bba6c359047c30a6291c43ceae376
    18 MIROC/MIROC6
2 088e06e115819c0c037a4fe3014635cecc25e7b4bf7dc3cdb3b66d53247470c1
5f88aacbbda189bf3f5ad7ac263e5bc93587418d2f6f3e07e9fbd643078f2af5
    34 CNRM-CERFACS/CNRM-CM6-1
    18 CNRM-CERFACS/CNRM-ESM2-1
2 0dfb44234ac0c3a4d452e58032bbe27f05089a4b7a13f978d07f6b30f4ecda7b
eabb95c0b0dfdebe27aaffbaab3682e480efe77abeb77ebb28ed23c1726a50fb
    10 NCAR/cesm2
    2 NCAR/cesm2-waccm
    2 NCAR/cesm2-waccm-fv2
2 0ebafe25dfb6f1ba1ce96b3aff301dcf6b4f695e3cd76a46c47ce9080c1e0776
5d5b6857ff1905dd59f1835fc64da7e1cfbc85843c435dd2b3b0a03a975120c5
    2 HAMMOZ-Consortium/MPI-ESM-1-2-HAM
    2 MPI-M/MPI-ESM1-2-LR
2 168c16f4b6b1e3f959f6760eb7991ed2c00c2ea3f689a6bde73b468b1842f0a7
e8c3a7c6c7f58885fb0a34e54f7ba3ce6bf99e016bbf441b9e33aa1c13872536
    2 NCC/NorESM2-LM
```

2 NCC/NorESM2-MM
2 497d66155af7e43705b70273a7bc76b7021256aa1f226ebba5e9de965a9b5f95
68bc857b7a583bf3e9c57c76d4ab1f2d8ef609de497f2f02defba521fba8c674
2 CCCma/CanESM5
2 5a55be04962c31204bfe4b4b9d3a6c0af0ebf6432472dff0a6417feca43b029
1fe0181e474a980905f8b0e24110532025ba8192f36b480b48552af03fab0294
1 MOHC/HadGEM3-GC31-LL
1 MOHC/UKESM1-0-LL
2 86d17acf6cff3cfeaa8c747429c7a422e05cc9541f894ae6b56fc888070f9cc
40d09f21af7cd734e45e3f9f3ee42ae43059f9aa4629c24bafba3e610c680d1e
1 CAS/FGOALS-f3-L
2 870fff0f2d4abdeafc173921b8437868bf801806c3694bbf6c5639216d47bb9b
6417a4f4f4b165396beb433aac84cf5f238b5733b199b56f45db6c709295ca31
1 EC-Earth-Consortium/EC-Earth3
1 EC-Earth-Consortium/EC-Earth3-Veg
1 EC-Earth-Consortium/EC-Earth3-Veg-LR
2 870fff0f2d4abdeafc173921b8437868bf801806c3694bbf6c5639216d47bb9b
f40cf5ef8a3131d771ec4767d1d1024f73d42a306f69195d12ab52c41df8bb80
2 CMCC/CMCC-CM2-SR5
2 978e1411f4b543a1c8805c1b800051628eb46c77ca992966bae4ab50f0074abe
f7cd95cf0373c625b65f7d97d2601ea3896e77cfbdad590cf315ba54ed788109
1 NCAR/CESM2-FV2
2 a4869d1d5aca4f8eab94cd56435e552b6192c4513913b6258c775d9b8157b5d2
4153098c6728aee22bb137d4895b3eae2062df3f08a5d0f8036afd43f61f44fc
1 NCAR/CESM2-FV2
2 a52180e0aa32620867ee7c4ec252e36a5ae83849529653880369160d8ee2306e
95fcafce63afdf40304c4daa9c950abb138828de773627c2ee3a25fe8aaf0abc
1 MOHC/HadGEM3-GC31-MM
2 beb782131c8382cddae5c6e5dc0dd9c94155c62f41fd15c1acd710df90726923
300059fbc8d04014c07cc7ba890e1da2c6c09f7b4e106d91edb5eb4a37b7312
2 NCC/NorCPM1
2 de47725a345cdc439d11ea2420266836810b2cb9f03c499f722a908ceb2ed26a
c1bed0ec8e3b3f42c319eff370c64bf271fefe60f496c20c2fba0e56257992e3
376 IPSL/IPSL-CM6A-LR
2 dec6b24fadf78f2f9eadd47bf7e112ea62e83f7ba92cde76aeed27f4975c06b1
e70334e752d0e89aaefef40d00d16669c82c5daacd8ec65b06853d6e0e5037ee
2 SNU/SAM0-UNICON
2 THU/CIESM
2 e451c006ea8bcd61ba78f2e9d909ba4f7f3aca98320183d2aa1afe2484455cc
a271a82c4cde9f768ac8ceabe54f85b2c5c2bbfdbbc606534004a93b76c55ae13
2 MRI/MRI-ESM2-0
2 e86f2c28e0372497ebb36b9bd820cdcd0841d0262b7c3f3535648ebd7e2efa2c
3a7af9a34d0cd22e194a51c1e2ecd37efd1c16579b1124b289637113088b148f
1 NOAA-GFDL/GFDL-ESM4
2 f3381b28f617397a3214731f38adca95dbcf1a124d5d394856e1043817022e41
193661f2945f291b17261b4829b20718bffae20c99dd5ed30e104a9a815a02ca
2 CSIRO/ACCESS-ESM1-5
2 CSIRO-ARCCSS/ACCESS-CM2

2 f442fbae61558d949bf6235d8db42a3f836b5f1dd58a12b4b9dae425c227f078
eabb95c0b0dfdebe27aaffbaab3682e480efe77abeb77ebb28ed23c1726a50fb
1 NCAR/CESM2

2 fa5d9e67dcd6c4e48d82cf54fc5a23eb249bd61e4c7857ea42a84f97939bd7dc
c3ab14a69527223508947d3f56f63d2f6d238d524ca9b340662c69f7eebd345a
2 MPI-M/MPI-ESM1-2-HR

B Using source_id CV

https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP6_CVs/blob/master/CMIP6_source_id.json

```
"model_component":{
  "aerosol":{
    "description":"MA
SINGAR mk2r4 (TL95; 192 x 96 longitude/latitude; 80 levels; top level 0.01 hPa)",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"250 km"
  },
  "atmos":{
    "description":"MRI-AGCM3.5 (TL159; 320 x 160 longitude/latitude; 80 levels; top level 0.01
hPa)",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"100 km"
  },
  "atmosChem":{
    "description":"MRI-CCM2.1 (T42; 128 x 64 longitude/latitude; 80 levels; top level 0.01 hPa)",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"250 km"
  },
  "land":{
    "description":"HAL 1.0",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"100 km"
  },
  "landIce":{
    "description":"none",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"none"},
  "ocean":{ "description":"MRI.COM4.4 (tripolar primarily 0.5 deg latitude/1 deg longitude with
meridional refinement down to 0.3 deg within 10 degrees north and south of the equator; 360
x 364 longitude/latitude; 61 levels; top grid cell 0-2 m)",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"100 km"},
  "ocnBgchem":{ "description":"MRI.COM4.4",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"100 km" },
  "seaIce":{ "description":"MRI.COM4.4",
    "native_nominal_resolution":"100 km"
  }
}
```

C : Using ES-DOC

<https://explore.es-doc.org/cmip6/models/mri/mri-esm2-0>

MRI > MRI-ESM2.0 :: Ocean > Grid

Top Level Properties

Grid > Name	
Description	Name of grid in ocean model.
Value	--
Grid > Overview	
Description	Overview of grid in ocean model.
Value	--
Discretisation	
Discretisation > Vertical > Coordinates	
Description	Type of vertical coordinates in ocean
Value	Z*-coordinate
Discretisation > Vertical > Partial Steps	
Description	Using partial steps with Z or Z* vertical coordinate in ocean ?
Value	TRUE
Discretisation > Horizontal > Type	
Description	Horizontal grid type
Value	Two north poles (ORCA-style)
Discretisation > Horizontal > Staggering	
Description	Horizontal grid staggering type
Value	Arakawa B-grid
Discretisation > Horizontal > Scheme	
Description	Horizontal discretisation scheme in ocean
Value	Finite difference

MRI > MRI-ESM2.0 :: Atmosphere > Grid

Top Level Properties

Grid > Name	
Description	Name of grid in atmosphere model.
Value	TL159LB0
Grid > Overview	
Description	Overview of grid in atmosphere model.
Value	--
Discretisation	
Discretisation > Horizontal > Scheme Type	
Description	Horizontal discretisation type
Value	Spectral
Discretisation > Horizontal > Scheme Method	
Description	Horizontal discretisation method
Value	-- Awaiting modelling group input --
Discretisation > Horizontal > Scheme Order	
Description	Horizontal discretisation function order
Value	-- Awaiting modelling group input --
Discretisation > Horizontal > Horizontal Pole	
Description	Horizontal discretisation pole singularity treatment
Value	--
Discretisation > Horizontal > Grid Type	
Description	Horizontal grid type
Value	Gaussian
Discretisation > Vertical > Coordinate Type	
Description	Type of vertical coordinate system
Value	Hybrid sigma-pressure - sigma system near terrain and isobaric above